

DEVELOPMENT OF A SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SOURCE USING HYDROGEN FUEL CELL

By

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the development of a sustainable energy source using hydrogen fuel cell. The developed system comprises of a chemical cell that converts the hydrogen of a cell in presence of oxidizing agent (often oxygen) into electricity through a pair of redox reactions. The basic materials of the system include; an anode, a cathode and an electrolyte that allows ions often positively charged hydrogen ions (protons) to move between the two sides of the fuel cell. At the anode, a catalyst causes the fuel to undergo oxidation reactions that generate ions and electrons. The ion moves from the anode to the cathode through the electrolyte. At the same time, electron flow the anode to the cathode through an external circuit producing direct current. At the cathode another catalyst causes ions, electrons and oxygen to react, forming water and possibly other product. These are different from batteries in requiring a continuous source of hydrogen fuel and oxygen (usually from air) to sustain the chemical reaction, whereas in a battery, the chemical energy usually comes from substances that are already present in the battery. Hydrogen fuel cell can be used to generate power for commercial, industrial and residential buildings as well as to power fuel cell vehicles, including buses, trains, boats etc.

Keywords: Fuel cell, hydrogen, sustainable energy, catalyst and environmentally-friendly

INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen fuel cell is one of the sustainable energy sources that is environmentally friendly through decarbonization of the ozone layer. According to French chemist (Kreth, 2004), “hydrogen” is named after two Greek words “hydro” meaning water and “genes” meaning born or formed. However, hydrogen is the first element on the periodic table. Since, hydrogen cannot be found in a free state but

in combined state, this element, exhibit both physical and chemical properties as it is obtainable in other elements in the periodic table.

Hydrogen makes up of 75% of normal matter by mass and over 90% by number of atoms. This element is found in great abundance in stars and sun (US energy formation 2004). Hydrogen, the lightest chemical element with symbol H^{++} has an atomic number one. It occurs as the diatomic molecule (H_2). And consists of a single proton. In other words, its atom consists of one proton (nucleus) and one electron with relative mass of 1.00797g/mol. Hydrogen fuel cell technology converts the chemical energy in hydrogen into electricity through an electrochemical reaction with oxygen, producing only water and heat as by-products making it a clean energy source.

Key advantages of using hydrogen fuel cell include zero emissions of point-of-use, high efficiency compared to combustion engines and scalability for various uses. Hydrogen fuel cell is key technology for a sustainable energy future (<https://www.energy.gov>. 2025). Throughout the universe, hydrogen is mostly found in the atomic and plasma state. As a plasma, hydrogen electron and proton are not bound together, resulting in very high electrical conductivity and high emissive, producing the light from the sun and stars. (Guala, 2004). Hydrogen is found in the neutral atomic state in the interstellar medium in abundant quantity (United State department of energy 2007)

According to Edward & Mike (2008), over 95% of the hydrogen produced in United State is through the process of steam reforming which is the method of producing hydrogen from fossil fuel or hydrocarbons. The steaming reacts with methane to yield carbon-monoxide and hydrogen

Kari-Appa 2023, stated that among different fuel cell type, hydrogen fuel cell is an appealing option for powering future automobiles and power generation.

METHODOLOGY

- **Materials**

The basics components of the hydrogen fuel cell system are;

- i. **Anode:** where the hydrogen gas is supplied and split into proton and electron
- ii. **Cathode:** where oxygen gas combines with electrons and protons to form water.
- iii. **Electrolyte:** a medium that allows only ions (proton) to pass through, forcing electrons to travel through an external circuit generating electricity
- iv. **Fuel cell tests hard ware:** used for proven design development and proofing new catalysts, membranes gas diffusion layer (GDL) materials and for identification of optimal/limitations of the tested components.

- v. **Hydrogen tank:** is the cylindrical shape for storing hydrogen. A single standard K-bottle of ultra-high purity hydrogen should contain about 5500 liters of hydrogen and should be charged to 2300 Psi. And must be fitted with a pressure regulator to go from the tank pressure down to the operating pressure of the fuel cell.
- vi. **Graphite flow fluid (Stack):** this material is added together to boost the power output.
- vii. **Membrane Electrode Assemblies (MEA):** is the core component of the fuel cell and helps facilitate the electrochemical reactions that are needed to separate and recombine protons and electrons. There are different types based on layers (figure.1)

Figure 1: Diagram of different layer-type (Source: fuelcellset.com, 2024)

- **Methods**

The hydrogen from the fitted hydrogen tank, in the presence of oxygen is separated into proton and electron when passing through a catalyst (MEA). The reaction at the anode and cathode were;

(2)

On the anode side, hydrogen diffuses to the anode catalyst where it later dissociates into protons and electrons. These protons react with oxidants causing them to become what is commonly known as multi-facilitated proton membranes. The proton is conducted through the membrane to the cathode, while the electrons are forced to travel through a circuit (figure 2), converting it into electrical power energy. And on the cathode catalyst, oxygen molecules react with electrons and protons to form water.

Figure 2: Diagram of hydrogen fuel cell generating electricity

DISCUSSION

This process efficiently converts the chemical energy of the hydrogen into electrical energy with water and heat as the only by-products as showed in equation 4 above, making it environmentally friendly. The device operates at the temperate of about -80% with an efficiency of 60%, and varies based on application and operating conditions.

CONCLUSION

Hydrogen fuel cells technology has evolved from experimental prototypes to commercially practical energy solutions with applications in power generation, transportation and industry. Their ability to provide clean, efficient and scalable power makes the fuel cell an important technology in the transition toward sustainable energy. While challenges such as infrastructural development, hydrogen production and policies are to be enhanced.

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